

Happiness of secondary level students of Sikkim

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12529657>

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Abstract

The present study is intended to examine the levels of happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim. The sample comprised 200 adolescents from all the districts of Sikkim. Happiness scale developed by Ayophika Wallang and Dr. Rihunlang Rymbai (2021) was used to collect the data. Descriptive and inferential statistics namely mean, S.D, t-test was used for attaining the objectives of the study.

The primary objective of the present study was to study the happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim, in terms of gender and locale of secondary school students of Sikkim. The findings of the present study revealed that significant differences were found with regard to locale but no significant difference were found in the happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with reference to gender.

Keywords: Happiness, secondary school students

Introduction

Positive psychology is a relatively young branch of Psychology. It has its roots in the beliefs of various philosophers, including Epicurus and Aristotle, as well as the precepts of several religions, including Buddhism, Christianity, and Judaism. Formal studies started by Humanistic psychologists such as Abraham Maslow and Carl Rogers. Some unique theories of happiness were developed by some positive psychologists such as Flow Theory developed by Csikszentmihalyi (2002) ^[14], Authentic Happiness Theory and Well-Being Theory (PERMA Model).

Aristotle said, "Happiness is the meaning and the purpose of life, the whole aim and end of human existence. It is a subjective feeling, a state of mind that lies within every human being. It is not only a pleasure but beyond that. It is correctly said that happiness is the meaning and purpose of life (cited in Nanda, 2020) ^[5]. Hedonic and eudaimonic are the two popular theories of happiness in psychology. While eudaimonic happiness is attained via experiences of meaning and purpose, hedonic happiness is attained through experiences of pleasure and enjoyment. In different ways, both types of happiness are attained and contribute to overall well-being in different ways. (Vinney, 2020) ^[12].

The main objective of this study is to find the level of

happiness of secondary school students in Sikkim. It aims to find the difference in the happiness of secondary school students with reference to gender and locale.

In addition to the challenges of learning and achievement, students come to school with stressors arising from many sources including family system disturbances, peer interaction conflicts, social-cultural components, and vulnerabilities to physical and mental health risk factors. Therefore, education should not only promote development in cognition, language, literacy, numeracy, and the arts but also address the well-being and happiness of the students. Thus, a combination of building capabilities in scholastic areas of literacy, mathematics, science, and other subjects with a huge emphasis on co-scholastic skills of mindfulness, self-awareness, critical thinking, reflection, and inner stability seems to be the need for an hour (Bhat, 2021) ^[11]. Education has a larger purpose to serve and hence, it cannot be seen in isolation from the dire needs of today's society. Educators and schools across the globe are realizing the need for a wellness lesson for school children (Sisodia, 2019) ^[9, 10].

Review of Literature

Usha Rani, K (2011) ^[11] studied on Happiness in adolescents. The findings of the study revealed that

adolescents girls are happier than boys with their immediate family relatives and significant others, they are also happier in the choice of their leisure activities and the things they indulge in the study, the study also found that adolescents studying in day schools are significantly happier than the boarding schools adolescents on the leisure domain, the junior children were happier than their seniors on the relationship and the leisure of happiness.

Mehrdadi *et al.*, (2016)^[4] in their study on Factors Affecting Happiness: A Cross Sectional Study in the Iranian Youth. The findings of the study revealed that the place of residence, age group, type of occupation, and physical activity were factors associated with happiness in young persons, the results also found that there was a significant relationship between the happiness score and location in urban and rural area but no significant difference was found in terms of gender, marital status and education level with happiness in young persons.

Chui and Wong (2016)^[15] conducted a study on Gender Differences in Happiness and Life Satisfaction among Adolescents in Hong Kong: Relationships and Self Concept. The population of the study consists of 1428 adolescents in Hong Kong. The study uses a survey method and the results found that the association of gender with happiness and life satisfaction through relationship style and self-concept.

Jhilik and Lalit (2017)^[16] conducted a study to determine the level of Happiness among students in higher education. The results showed that there is no significant difference in happiness among undergraduate and postgraduate students with respect to gender, level of education, stream, or family income, the study also found that there is a significant difference in happiness between the students who live in rural area and the students who live in an urban area.

Pakira and Mohakud (2017)^[6] conducted a study to determine the level of Happiness among students in higher education. The results showed that most of the students i.e. 79% possessed average happiness level (50%) to higher, 22% possessed below average and highest (3%) happiness levels and an almost negligible percentage of students i.e. 1.4% showed low happiness level.

Lumontod (2018)^[3] in the study found that female students are happier than male students and also overall students have a high level of Happiness.

Parmar and Vyas (2018)^[7] conducted a study on 'A Comparative Study of Happiness among Adolescents'. The study investigates to compare happiness among girls and boys adolescents of higher secondary student. The results of the study showed that significant differences were found between girls and boys in the levels of their Happiness.

Pahsyntiew and Rymbai (2019)^[8] conducted a study on the Happiness of female higher-secondary students. The sample comprise female higher secondary students selected through stratified random sampling. The study revealed that the majority of the female higher secondary students have an average Happiness.

Need and Importance of the Study

Adolescence is a unique stage of human development and an important time for laying the foundations of good health. It is the period when adolescents experience rapid biological and psychological changes. Education has to train individuals on how to develop and preserve individual

health. Education aims to provide healthy personality for an individual which is one of the important ingredients of education. According to the World Happiness Report 2015, schools that prioritize learner well-being have the potential to be more effective, with better learning outcomes and greater achievements in learners' lives (Helliwell, *et al.*, 2015 as cited in Sisodia, 2019)^[9, 10]. Happiness is considered to be particularly important in adolescents due to its contribution to their future success.

Happy people tend to be successful in many facets of life, including the social, professional, and family spheres. Due to their stronger immune systems and longer life spans than those who are depressed and miserable, they typically lead healthier physical lives. They are more helpful and pro social, and they are more adept at handling difficult circumstances (cited in Nanda 2020)^[5].

Happiness is considered to be particularly important in adolescents due to its contribution to their future success. When the children are happy, they quicken to solve the problems. They are more open to critical thought and reasoning, and their aims towards life are better lived. A Happy student keeps themselves motivated in any walk of their life, be it at institutions learning centers, or in building good relationships with classmates. They can troubleshoot and solve both social and academic dilemmas (Jhilik and Lalit 2017)^[16]. Happiness promotes healthy well-being, better work performance, warmth, altruism, creative and innovative thinking, and problem-solving attitudes and reduces stress overall (cited in Jhilik and Lalit 2017)^[16]. For a prosperous and overall development of the future, happiness is the most fundamental need for every child. A happy student has a stronger immune system which ultimately leads to a longer life span in contrast to the depressed and unhappy ones.

The topic 'Happiness of Secondary Level Students of Sikkim' is a need of an hour. The Investigator feels that this topic does not just benefit the students but can be more beneficial to society and the state.

Statement of the Problem

The aim of the study is to explore the happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with regard to locale and gender to make the students aware of their level of happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim. On, the basis of the rationale of this study the problem is stated as 'Happiness of Secondary Level Students of Sikkim'.

Operational Definition

Happiness: Happiness is the experience of positive well-being (cited in Wallang, 2021)^[13]. The elements of well-being include PERMA- Positive Emotions, Engagement, Relationship, Meaning and Accomplishment.

Secondary School Students

Students, who are studying in IX and X belonging to the age group of 14 to 18, are secondary school students.

Objectives

1. To study the overall level of happiness of secondary school students in Sikkim.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference in happiness of secondary school students in Sikkim

with reference to gender [Male/Female].

- To check whether there is any significant difference among rural and urban secondary school students in Sikkim.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean score of Happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim in terms of locale.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean score of Happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim in terms of gender.

Materilas and Methods

To study the happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim in terms of gender and locale, the researcher has used the Descriptive Survey research method.

Population: The population of this study comprised male and female students of class IX Government Secondary and Senior Secondary Schools located in rural and urban areas of Sikkim.

Sample

The sample for the present study was taken from different

government senior and secondary schools in Sikkim. The sample comprised 200 secondary and senior secondary school students of class IX. The investigator selected the schools from each district considering the locale.

Sampling Technique

The investigator used a stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample.

Tool used for the study

Happiness: Happiness scale developed by Ayophika W. Pahsyntiew and Rihunlang Rymbai (2021) ^[13]. The test has 42 items. It was standardized on 1,580 Higher Secondary Students who were drawn from the different Higher Secondary Schools and Colleges from the Higher Secondary Section run by colleges from the three districts of Meghalaya namely East Khasi Hills, West Jaintia Hills, and West Garo Hills.

Data Analysis

Objective 1

To study the level of happiness of secondary school students in Sikkim.

To test the above hypothesis t-test has been done. The outcome of this analysis is shown in the following table-1.

Table 1: Showing the level of Happiness of Secondary School students of Sikkim.

SL. No	Raw score Range of Full Scale	Z-Score Range	F	F %	Level of Happiness
1.	181 & above	+2.01 & above	08	4	Very High
2.	166 to 180	+1.1 to + 2.00	36	18	High
3.	134 to 165	-1.0 to + 1.0	142	71	Average
4.	120 to 133	-1.1 to - 2.0	10	5	Low
5.	119 & below	-2.1 & below	04	2	Very Low
			200	100%	

Fig 1: A bar graph showing the level of Happiness of Secondary School Students of Sikkim.

Results

The above table 1 and figure no 1 revealed the level of Happiness of secondary school students in percentage. It was found that 4% of secondary school students have a very high level of happiness, 18% have a high level of happiness but 71% of secondary school students have an average level of happiness, 5% of secondary school students have a low level of happiness and 2% of secondary school students have a very low level of happiness.

Objective 2: To study the level of happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with reference to gender. To find out gender differences in the level of happiness of secondary school students, mean, S.D, T-value were computed and the following table shows the result.

Table 2: Showing happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with reference to gender.

Variable	Group	N	Mean	S.D	Critical Value of t	t-value	Remarks
Happiness	Male	100	154.69	13.7	1.97	0.43	Not significant
	Female	100	155.57	15.4			

** - Not significant at 0.05 level

** Confirming studies: Rymbai (2019) [8]; Pahsyntiew and Rymbai (2019) [8]; Wallang (2021) [13]

Fig 2: Showing the difference in Mean & Standard deviation of male and female secondary school students in terms of Happiness.

Results

Gender: The "t" test of mean scores between the male and female was calculated and the result obtained showed "t" value 0.43 which was not significant at 0.05 level (1.97), the perusal of Table 2 and Figure 2 indicated that there was no significant difference in the happiness of students in terms of gender. However, female secondary school students have a slightly higher level of Happiness than male secondary school students.

Hence, the hypothesis (H₀₁) which stated that "there is no significant difference in the mean score of Happiness of secondary school students with reference to gender" was accepted.

Objective 3: To study the level of happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with reference to locale.

Table 3: Showing happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with reference to locale.

Variable	Group	N	Mean	S.D	Critical Value of t	tvalue	Remarks
Happiness	Rural	100	154.69	13.7	1.97	3.691	Significant
	Urban	100	147.23	14.85			

** - Significant at 0.05 level

** Confirming studies: Mehrdadi *et al.*, (2016) [4]; Jhilik and Lalit (2017) [16].

Fig 3: A bar graph showing the mean score and SD of happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim with reference to locale.

Results

Locale: The "t" test of mean scores between the urban and rural was calculated and the result obtained showed a "t" value 3.691 which was significant at 0.05 level (1.97), the perusal of Table no 3 and Figure 3 indicated that there was a significant difference in the happiness of students in terms of rural and urban, the rural students (154.69) have higher level of happiness than of urban secondary students (147.23). Hence, the hypothesis (H₀₂) which stated that "there is no significant difference in the mean score of Happiness of secondary school students with reference to locale" was rejected.

Discussion

In this study, it has been found that the majority of secondary school students of Sikkim male and female have average levels of happiness. This finding is aligned with the findings of Rymbai (2019) [8]; Pahsyntiew and Rymbai (2019) [8], and Wallang (2021) [13] who found that the majority of the students have an average Happiness. The present study states that there is no significant difference between the male and female secondary school students with regard to their level of happiness, the result of the study was also supported by Malik, S. (2013) [17] even (Diener *et al.*, as cited in Mehrdadi *et al.*, 2016) [4] suggested that happiness levels are equal among men and women. Researchers have also made some efforts to compare the happiness of adolescents in relation to gender. In this regard, the past studies have all found a significant difference between girls and boys (Usha Rani, K, 2011; Parmar and Vyas, 2018) [11, 7]. The findings from these studies revealed that adolescent girls are happier than boys, they are also happier in the choice of their leisure activities and the things they indulge in the study. When comparing the mean scores

of rural and urban locale of secondary school students, the investigator found that rural secondary school students are better in their level of happiness, this could be because of a good school environment, less competition, students being more connected with the nature, less pressure from the parents, moreover rural students do not frequently use social media. These findings are in line with the findings of, Pakira and Mohakud (2017) ^[6], but the results of the study contradict the result of a study conducted by Mehrdadi *et al.*, (2016) ^[4] who revealed that though there is a significant difference between the rural and urban adolescents but compare to rural, urban adolescents are slightly happier than rural adolescents.

Findings

1. The happiness of secondary school students of Sikkim was found average.
2. No significant difference was found in the mean score of happiness of secondary school students in terms of gender.
3. Significant difference was found in the mean score of happiness of rural and urban secondary school students of Sikkim.

Educational Implications

1. This study will be helpful for the administrators, policymakers, teachers, parents, curriculum framers, and counselors associated with school education.
2. It also contributes to better health, better learning, higher emotional literacy, social-emotional learning, and also in good behavior.
3. It helps in creating happy environment which plays a major role in the overall well-being, success, and achievements of children in school as well as life beyond.
4. This study will help to bridge the gap between the teachers and the students, and will create a safer and a non-judgmental atmosphere in the school.
5. Thus, this study will also boost the self confidence or likability of the students.

Conclusion

Thus, from the above findings and interpretations of the study, the investigator would like to suggest to all the concerned educators that teachers must invest some time to get to know their students. They can make an effort to know the context of every student and create the opportunity to make use of humor inside the classroom also school curriculum can incorporate mindful meditation/ quiet time. Schools can give input on how to enhance positive emotional experiences. To conclude the investigator would like to quote Nelson Mandela 'Education is the most powerful weapon which can be used to change the world'. Given their importance for the future mental health of our nations or state happiness and well-being skills deserve to be taken seriously- and teachers can lead the charge, one classroom at a time.

Reference

1. Bhat M. International Journal of Recent Scientific Research. June 2013. Available from: <http://www.recentscientific.com>

2. Kye SY, Park KH. Psychosocial factors and health behavior among Korean adults: a cross-sectional study. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.* 2012;13(1):49-56.
3. Lumontod R. Happiness and other factors behind examination performance of college students. *Int J Res Stud Psychol.* 2018;7(2).
4. Mehrdadi A, Sadeghian S, Direkvand-Moghadam A, Hashemian A. Factors affecting happiness: a cross-sectional study in the Iranian youth. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2016;10(5).
5. Nanda GK. Happiness Is An Experience Attainable Through Love, Grace And Gratitude. *J Community Guidance Res.* 2020;37(1):109-140.
6. Pakira J, Mohakud LL. Happiness Among Students of Higher Education Level In West Bengal. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344229952> 2017.
7. Parmar KN, Vyas RM. A comparative study of happiness among adolescents. *Int. J Indian Psychol.* 2018;6(2):78-82. DOI:10.25215/0602.068
8. Pahsyntiew AW, Rymbai R. The happiness of female higher secondary students. *J Emerg Technol. Innov. Res (JETIR).* 2019;6(2).
9. Sisodia MM. DelE Education Department. Happiness Curriculum Framework. Available from: <http://edudel.nic.in>
10. Sisodia MM, Kumar MS, Srivastava MPS, Gupta MS. Dr. Sunita S. Kaushik, Director (SCERT); c2019.
11. UshaRani K. A study of happiness in adolescents. [Doctoral Thesis, Andhra University]; c2011. Available from: <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/385012>
12. Vinney C. What's the Difference Between Eudaimonic and Hedonic Happiness? Thought Co; c2020. Available from: <https://www.thoughtco.com/eudaimonic-and-hedonic-happiness-4783750>
13. Wallang Pahsyntiew A. Self-concept and happiness in relation to academic achievement among higher secondary students in Meghalaya. [PhD Thesis]. North Eastern Hill University. Available from; c2021: <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/387613>
14. Nakamura J, Csikszentmihalyi M. The concept of flow. *Handbook of positive psychology.* 2002;89:105.
15. Korhonen J, Tapola A, Linnanmäki K, Aunio P. Gendered pathways to educational aspirations: The role of academic self-concept, school burnout, achievement and interest in mathematics and reading. *Learning and Instruction.* 2016;46:21-33.
16. Jat ML, Datta A, Gathala MK, Jat HS, Sharma PC, Singh Y. Potassium dynamics and management under conservation agriculture in intensive cropping systems. *Advances IN.* 2017 Aug 28:16.
17. Jumani NB, Bhatti AJ, Malik S. Student Support in Higher Education: Lessons Learnt and Challenges Ahead. *International Journal of Technology and Educational Marketing (IJTEM).* 2013;3(1):77-88.

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